

Application modeling of flex-compressive piezoelectric energy harvesting cell in railway system

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A flex-compressive piezoelectric energy harvesting cell (F-C PEHC) with large load capacity and adjustable force transmission coefficient assembled from replaceable individual components has been proposed in previous research [1]. The Configurations of the F-C PEHC is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Configurations of the flex-compressive mode piezoelectric energy harvesting cell (F-C PEHC). (a) Prototype. (b) Individual Elements and the PZT stacks.

With different Element 1, i.e., Element 1a and 1b, the F-C PEHC could effectively weaken or enhance the applied mechanical load. Recently, we conducted an application modeling of the energy harvesting cell in railway system. The railway structure is assumed as a beam on a Winkler elastic foundation as shown in Figure 2, and the installation location of the energy harvesting cell is described in detail as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Schematic of railway track structure subjected to multiple moving loads.

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Figure 3. Installation detail of the F-C PEHC.

A train with five coaches presented in reference [2] is used in the energy harvesting modeling, and the geometric properties as well as the axle-loads are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Geometric properties and the axle-loads of the train with 5 coaches.

With the external resistor of $180\text{k}\Omega$, under 20 pairs of concentrated moving loads vary from 1.17kN to 1.80kN with the velocity of 30m/s , the simulated valid value of the output voltage and power are conducted respectively in the weakened and enhanced mode. Firstly, energy harvesting using the weakened mode F-C PEHC is proposed as shown in Figure 5. The generated voltage and power are 176 V and 0.34 W , respectively. Secondly, an energy harvesting system with the enhanced mode F-C PEHC is proposed as shown in Figure 6. The generated voltage and power are 186 V and 0.38 W , respectively. The present results indicate a great potential of the F-C PEHC in self-sustained monitoring in railway systems.

Figure 5. Time history of voltage and electric power (weakened mode). $v=30\text{m/s}$. $R=180\text{k}\Omega$

Figure 6. Time history of voltage and electric power (enhanced mode). $v=30\text{m/s}$. $R=180\text{k}\Omega$.

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- [2]. Wang J J, Shi Z F, Xiang H J, and Song G B 2015 Modeling on energy harvesting from a railway system using piezoelectric transducers *Smart Mater. Struct.* **24** 10501710.